

IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM AROUND THE WORLD AND IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: *This article explores the tourism industry is one of the most developed and significant industries in the world. Especially historical places and related monuments occupy an important place in the field of world tourism. The UN World Tourism Organization is a major world organization that promotes tourism in every country and organizes a tourism environment in the spirit of mutual respect and common human rights and peace for the population, regardless of nationality, religion, language, race, or origin. The main goal of this organization is to improve the health of the population and increase their interest in travel; to keep historical, spiritual, and cultural heritages in their original form throughout the ages and carry out propaganda about them throughout the world; and to promote the new culture through such tasks as the reproduction of monuments and the support of tourist agencies.*

Key words: *UN World Tourism Organization, developed tourist centers of the world, Samarkand in the eyes of the world, visit of Zurob Palolikashvili, attractions of Uzbekistan.*

Many developed countries around the world are famous for their tourism industries, and each of them has its mentality, customs, and historical places. In particular, the ancient city of Mexico is very famous for Chichen Itza. Russia has been able to attract tourists from all over the world with its wild nature. The oldest

and still-preserved monuments in Great Britain are located in the city of Stonehenge. Not only in these cities but also in Spain, Italy, Turkey, and other European countries, many places attract the attention of tourists.

In addition, such countries with a developed tourism sector are economically well-financed countries. One of the main state incomes comes from the state budget through this sector. At the same time, to develop tourism, the states will implement tasks such as increasing the number of tourism centers, maintaining constant contact with nationalities, further improving service areas, and making visa services cheaper and easier. According to statistics from 2017, the most developed country in the field of tourism is the United States, and its annual income in that year was 211 billion dollars, and we can understand that such a large income greatly contributes to the development of the country not only in the field of tourism but also in other areas.

At this point, it should be said that Uzbekistan is also paying great attention to this field, and with its many historical and memorial monuments, the world is at the center of attention.

We know that in ancient times, the countries of Asia and Central Asia were occupied by conquerors, and despite being hit by many blows, the preservation of historical monuments is amazing. Today, our country, with such a rich history, is becoming a tourist destination around the world. Every Uzbek is proud of the great history left by our ancestors. Especially in Bukhara, Samarkand, Tashkent, Khiva, Termiz, and Shakhrisabz regions, there are architectural monuments built by our ancestors. They were mainly created during the time of our ancestors, such as Amir Temur, Jalaluddin Manguberdi, Alisher Navoi, and Mirzo Ulugbek, and have a history of about 750 thousand years. All of them are included in the UNESCO World Heritage List and are legally insulated.

If we talk about the historical monuments of Uzbekistan, Samarkand is their pillar and the biggest. Today, this city, which has received the name "Savior of the Earth", is crowded with tourists. Samarkand has about 600 ha of historical monuments and modern and touristic centers and is famous for its rich history of

2750 years. Mainly, Registon, Amir Temur mausoleum, Bibi Khanim, Khoja Donyor Madrasa, the Mausoleum of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and Shahi Zinda are the faces of Samarkand. In addition, in this city, the "Great Silk Road International Tourism Center" serves more than 2 million tourists a year. Besides that, international festivals and Eastern concerts are held in our motherland. Of course, this is a happy situation for every child in Samarkand. The "Bakiy Shahar" tourist center, launched in 2022, has also attracted the attention of tourists.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, has turned Samarkand into a tourist center and announced that starting in August 2022, all international agreements and congresses will be held in Samarkand. One such agreement was recently signed on May 29, 2023, at the UN World Tourism Organization headquarters in Madrid, at the official signing ceremony of the agreement between the UN and Uzbekistan to hold the 25th session of the UNWTO General Assembly in Samarkand in October of this year, "Dunyo" AA reporter reports. UNWTO Secretary-General Zurob Palolikashvili, who visited Samarkand for the agreement, expressed his bright thoughts about Samarkand: "Uzbekistan is the heart of Central Asia, the keeper of a huge scientific, cultural, and architectural heritage. Today, Uzbekistan is a rapidly developing country; its economy is developing rapidly, and it is opening its powerful potential to the world. We observe that favorable conditions for the implementation of business initiatives are being formed, as a result of which the demand for foreign and domestic tourism is increasing rapidly. Uzbekistan is one of the recognized leaders in the field of tourism. At the same time, the tourism sector of Uzbekistan is one of the youngest sectors, but it is ahead of many other sectors in its development.

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